

Hitting the breaks. A comparison of pre-pandemic and lockdown behaviours among Romanian workers from home

ONLINE APPENDIX: COMPLETE STATISTICAL MODELS

Contents

Further description of the sample	2
Time worked in main job across Europe	3
Models for H1-H3	5
All sample	5
Models excluding the ones that reported more than 80 hours worked per week	7
Models for H1-H3: marginal effects in OLS models	9
Logit models for taking breaks	11
Models for the pooled sample	11
Separated models for 2018 and 2020	12
Models for taking breaks during 2020 lockdown, depending on previous experience of working from home	15

Further description of the sample

Figure A- 1 Distribution of number of hours worked **from home** (weekly) in the two waves of the survey

Figure A- 2 Distribution of **total** number of hours worked (weekly) in the two waves of the survey

While the distribution of total worked hours differs mainly by including some that work very few hours, the number of hours worked from home was larger in 2020 (during lockdown).

Time worked in main job across Europe

Figure A- 3 Average number of hours worked by week across Europe (main job only, data for 2018)

Variable LFSA_EWHAN2 in the Eurostat database
(https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsa_ewhan2/)

Figure A- 4 Average number of hours worked by week across Europe (main job only, data for 2020)

Variable LFSA_EWHAN2 in the Eurostat database
(https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsa_ewhan2/)

Models for H1-H3

All sample

Table A- 1. Ordered logit models (the same as table 2 in the main text)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
income	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	0.62	0.59 [†]	0.62	0.68
Education:				
BA	2.20	3.54	2.23	1.63
MA	1.96	3.21	2.01	1.61
PhD	2.80	4.35 [†]	2.79	2.06
marital Status:				
married	0.30 ^{**}	0.31 ^{**}	0.28 ^{**}	0.45
with partner	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.80
divorced/separated/widowed	2.37	2.47	2.28	4.54 [†]
one child	1.47	1.49	1.15	0.88
Children:				
2+ children	1.68	1.76	2.02	0.50
Age	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.66
Age # Age				1.01
number of people in the household				1.57 [*]
lives in Romania/Moldova	0.58	0.55	0.60	0.65
total worked hours (weekly)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98
hours worked from home (weekly)	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²		1.00	1.00	1.00
WfH2020	1.05	5.49	0.96	0.01
Interactions effects:				
WfH2020 # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00			
WfH2020 # BA		0.18		
WfH2020 # MA		0.18		
WfH2020 # PhD		0.20		
WfH2020 # one child			1.69	
WfH2020 # 2+ children			0.72	
WfH2020 # Age				1.30
WfH2020 # Age # Age				1.00
/				
cut1	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 [†]
cut2	0.07 [*]	0.09 [*]	0.07 [*]	0.00
cut3	0.21	0.29	0.23	0.00
Observations	218	218	218	154
Pseudo R ²	0.064	0.066	0.066	0.076

Exponentiated coefficients. Reference categories: men, no university degree, single, no children, lives abroad,

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table A- 2. OLS models -- all respondents

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
income	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	0.00
woman	-0.20	-0.20	-0.18	-0.13
Education:				
BA	0.26	0.48	0.25	0.21
MA	0.20	0.45	0.21	0.19
PhD	0.45	0.63 [†]	0.37	0.32
marital Status:				
married	-0.55 ^{**}	-0.47 [*]	-0.51 ^{**}	-0.34
with partner	-0.36 [†]	-0.32 [†]	-0.32 [†]	-0.14
divorced/separated/widowed	0.27	0.36 [†]	0.34	0.48
one child	0.11	0.14	0.02	-0.05
Children:				
2+ children	0.11	0.17	0.24	-0.29
Age	-0.00	-0.01	-0.01	-0.08
Age # Age				0.00
number of people in the household				0.17 ^{**}
lives in Romania/Moldova	-0.19	-0.27	-0.22	-0.15
total worked hours (weekly)	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	-0.01
hours worked from home (weekly)	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.00
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.00
WfH2020	-0.36	0.87	0.01	-0.11
Interactions effects:				
WfH2020 # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.03 [†]			
WfH2020 # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	-0.00 [*]			
WfH2020 # BA		-0.82		
WfH2020 # MA		-0.84		
WfH2020 # PhD		-0.84		
WfH2020 # one child			0.23	
WfH2020 # 2+ children			-0.14	
WfH2020 # Age				0.01
WfH2020 # Age # Age				-0.00
Constant	2.90 ^{***}	2.76 ^{***}	2.89 ^{***}	3.61 [†]
Observations	218	218	218	154
Adjusted R ²	0.070	0.051	0.055	0.011

Reference categories: men, no university degree, single, no children, lives abroad,

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Models excluding the ones that reported more than 80 hours worked per week

Table A- 3. Ordered logit

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
income	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	0.57 [†]	0.54 [†]	0.57 [†]	0.68
Education:				
BA	2.69	4.16	2.59	1.51
MA	2.46	4.12	2.39	1.55
PhD	3.72	5.39 [†]	3.48	1.99
marital Status:				
married	0.26 ^{**}	0.27 ^{**}	0.24 ^{**}	0.53
with partner	0.44 [†]	0.43 [†]	0.42 [†]	0.81
divorced/separated/widowed	2.53	2.35	2.26	4.81 [†]
one child	1.53	1.48	1.13	0.82
Children:				
2+ children	1.96	1.87	2.60	0.50
Age	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.65
Age # Age				1.01
number of people in the household				1.50 [†]
lives in Romania/Moldova	0.64	0.59	0.64	0.61
total worked hours (weekly)	0.97 [†]	0.98	0.98	0.98
hours worked from home (weekly)	0.99	1.03	1.02	1.02
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²		1.00	1.00	1.00
WfH2020	0.50	6.07	0.91	0.01
Interactions effects:				
WfH2020 # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.02			
WfH2020 # BA		0.16		
WfH2020 # MA		0.14		
WfH2020 # PhD		0.19		
WfH2020 # one child			1.75	
WfH2020 # 2+ children			0.52	
WfH2020 # Age				1.31
WfH2020 # Age # Age				1.00
/				
cut1	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 ^{***}	0.00 [*]
cut2	0.04 ^{**}	0.12	0.09 [*]	0.00
cut3	0.12 [†]	0.38	0.28	0.00
Observations	210	210	210	149
Pseudo R ²	0.065	0.068	0.070	0.066

Exponentiated coefficients. Reference categories: men, no university degree, single, no children, lives abroad,

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table A- 4. OLS models

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
income	0.00	-0.00	-0.00	0.00
woman	-0.21	-0.23 [†]	-0.21	-0.14
Education:				
BA	0.31	0.59	0.32	0.18
MA	0.26	0.59	0.29	0.17
PhD	0.53	0.74 [†]	0.47	0.30
marital Status:				
married	-0.59**	-0.54**	-0.58**	-0.28
with partner	-0.42*	-0.39*	-0.39*	-0.14
divorced/separated/widowed	0.27	0.31	0.29	0.50
one child	0.11	0.14	0.01	-0.08
Children:				
2+ children	0.14	0.20	0.33	-0.30
Age	-0.00	-0.01	-0.00	-0.11
Age # Age				0.00
number of people in the household				0.16*
lives in Romania/Moldova	-0.15	-0.23	-0.19	-0.17
total worked hours (weekly)	-0.01 [†]	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
hours worked from home (weekly)	-0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	0.00	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00
WfH2020	-0.80*	0.96	-0.01	-0.76
Interactions effects:				
WfH2020 # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.06*			
WfH2020 # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	-0.00 [†]			
WfH2020 # BA		-0.93		
WfH2020 # MA		-0.98		
WfH2020 # PhD		-0.89		
WfH2020 # one child			0.25	
WfH2020 # 2+ children			-0.26	
WfH2020 # Age				0.05
WfH2020 # Age # Age				-0.00
Constant	3.26***	2.57***	2.72***	4.12 [†]
Observations	210	210	210	149
Adjusted R ²	0.072	0.051	0.057	-0.014

Reference categories: men, no university degree, single, no children, lives abroad,

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Models for H1-H3: marginal effects in OLS models

Figure A- 5. Marginal effects on taking breaks (the figure is also reproduced in the main text)

Upper-left pane (worked hours) based on model (1). Upper-right pane (age) is based on model (2). Bottom-left pane (children) is based on model (3). Bottom-right pane (education) is based on model (4). For all panes, the Y-axes have the same categories, illustrated on the right.

The figure is also reproduced in the main text. We put it also here to facilitate quick comparison with Figure A- 6 (see next page).

Figure A- 6. Marginal effects on taking breaks – only those that did not report too long hours

Upper-left pane (worked hours) based on model (1). Upper-right pane (age) is based on model (2). Bottom-left pane (children) is based on model (3). Bottom-right pane (education) is based on model (4). For all panes, the Y-axes have the same categories, illustrated on the right.

Logit models for taking breaks

Models for the pooled sample

Table A- 5. Logit models for types of breaks, both WfH waves

	eat	relax	entertain	childcare	housework	rest
income	1.00*	1.00 [†]	1.00 [†]	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	0.88	0.64 [†]	0.35***	0.72	0.88	0.62*
BA	0.00***	1.21	2.66	0.93	8.0e+11***	0.54
MA	0.00***	0.65	1.42	1.29	5.4e+11***	0.41
PhD	0.00***	0.69	1.25	1.00	5.9e+11***	0.92
hours worked from home (weekly)	0.91***	1.01	1.03	0.96 [†]	13.50***	0.99
BA # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.08***	0.98*	0.95	0.99	0.07***	1.01
MA # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.11***	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.07***	1.03*
PhD # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.09***	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.07***	1.01
Age	0.95*	1.02	0.95*	0.83***	0.99	1.01
married	1.03	0.70	0.70	0.26*	0.70	0.81
with partner	0.57	0.71	0.92	0.40	0.78	1.29
divorced/separated/widowed	1.47	1.06	3.02**	1.20	1.19	0.92
one child	1.74	0.52	0.68	192.33***	0.88	0.62
2+ children	1.29	0.40*	0.53	184.62***	1.08	0.62
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.97 [†]	0.99	1.00	1.04 [†]	1.01	1.00
2+ children # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.04	1.00	0.99
lives in Romania/Moldova	1.00	0.83	0.52	0.14*	0.74	0.70
total worked hours (weekly)	1.01	1.00	0.99	1.01	1.00	1.00
WfH2020	2.66**	0.75	0.75	4.85***	0.69 [†]	0.86
Observations	204	218	218	210	218	218
Pseudo R ²	0.236	0.122	0.224	0.691	0.079	0.101

Exponentiated coefficients. Dependent variables: taking breaks for **eating**, **relaxation**, **entertainment**, **childcare**, **housework**, **resting**.

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Separated models for 2018 and 2020

Table A- 6. Logit models for types of breaks, WfH2018

	eat	relax	entertain	childcare	housework	rest
income	1.00	1.00*	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	1.01	0.44 [†]	0.40*	0.39	0.85	0.22**
BA	0.76	8.1e+12***	1.96	0.00***	7.9e+11***	0.14
MA	0.09*	5.7e+12***	0.63	0.00*	1.7e+12***	0.00**
PhD	2.95	5.3e+11***	0.57	1.00	1.0e+14***	1.00
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.11*	22.89***	1.01	0.38*	17.32***	0.65*
BA # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.80*	0.04***	0.96 [†]	226.83***	0.06***	1.23
MA # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.87 [†]	0.04***	1.01	2.93*	0.05***	1.59*
PhD # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.74*	0.06***	1.00	1.00	0.04***	1.00
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00***	0.98***		1.02**	0.98***	1.01*
BA # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00*	1.02***		0.85***	1.02***	0.99
MA # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00 [†]	1.02***		0.97**	1.02***	0.99*
PhD # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00 [†]	1.01*		1.00	1.02***	1.00
Age	0.98	1.00	0.98	0.84***	1.01	1.03
married	0.71	1.46	0.75	49.45*	0.69	0.86
with partner	0.59	0.37 [†]	1.10		0.51	0.71
divorced/separated/widowed	6.43 [†]	1.37	4.79*	64477.24**	1.00	2.45
one child	1.20	0.66	0.58		0.56	0.01*
2+ children	0.01*	0.19	0.62	0.00*	0.10	0.01*
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	0.95	1.00		1.02	1.53*
2+ children # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.81*	1.03	1.02	3.05**	1.21*	1.65 [†]
lives in Romania/Moldova	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.58	1.00
total worked hours (weekly)	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.93*	1.00	1.00
2+ children # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²				0.98*	1.00*	0.99 [†]
one child # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²					1.00	0.99*
Observations	98	98	98	41	92	93
Pseudo R ²	0.363	0.277	0.216	0.723	0.258	0.320

Exponentiated coefficients

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table A- 7. Logit models for types of breaks, WfH2020

	eat	relax	entertain	childcare	housework	rest
income	1.00	1.00 [†]	1.00	0.89	1.00	1.00
woman	1.17	0.74	0.29 ^{***}	.	0.88	0.90
BA	17.00	0.02 ^{***}	952.32 ^{***}		565.78 ^{***}	0.86
MA	0.31	0.01 ^{***}	466.87 ^{***}	0.00	478.56 ^{***}	0.59
PhD	1.00	0.01 ^{***}	597.84 ^{***}	9.e+144	231.63 ^{***}	1.00
hours worked from home (weekly)	0.96	0.78 ^{***}	1.40 ^{***}	0.01	1.34 ^{***}	0.99
BA # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.91 [†]	1.27 ^{***}	0.72 ^{***}		0.76 ^{***}	0.99
MA # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.03	1.30 ^{***}	0.74 ^{***}	2.4e+28	0.77 ^{***}	1.02
PhD # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.29 ^{***}	0.74 ^{***}	2.1e+08	0.79 ^{***}	1.00
Age	0.91 [†]	1.04 [†]	0.93 ^{**}	0.00	1.00	1.04
married	0.99	0.19 ^{***}	0.53		0.81	0.42
with partner	0.61	0.65	0.63	1.00	0.87	1.90
divorced/separated/widowed	1.22	0.76	1.55	0.00	0.59	0.51
one child	17.89	0.18 [†]	0.77		0.57	0.00 [*]
2+ children	4.e+166 ^{***}	0.80	0.48	.	0.91	0.00 ^{***}
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.78 [†]	1.05	1.00		1.00	1.60 [*]
2+ children # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.00 ^{***}	0.94	1.02	0.00	0.93	9.7e+71 ^{***}
[hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00	1.00		0.51	1.00 [*]	1.00
one child # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00 [†]	1.00			1.00	0.99 [*]
2+ children # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.80 ^{***}	1.00		18.05	1.00	0.17 ^{***}
lives in Romania/Moldova	1.00	1.60	0.98	1.00	0.58	1.92
total worked hours (weekly)	0.99	0.99	0.96	5.2e+30	1.02	0.95
MA # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²				0.48		1.00
PhD # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²				0.67		1.00
BA # [hours worked from home (weekly)] ²						1.00
Observations	104	116	116	40	116	114
Pseudo R ²	0.464	0.217	0.293	1.000	0.113	0.277

Exponentiated coefficients

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figure A- 7. Joint marginal effects of having children and number of hours worked from home on the likelihood to take various types of breaks (logit models)

* In each pane, the probability to take at least a break varies from 0 to 100%.

Models for taking breaks during 2020 lockdown, depending on previous experience of working from home

Table A- 8. Prediction of taking breaks depending on previous experience of work-from-home: all WfH2020 sample

	tobit	OLS	ologit
has experience of isolation	1.38	1.88*	1.38
knows someone with Covid-19 disease	0.84	0.70	0.84
income	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	0.84	0.80	0.84
BA	1.16	2.63	1.16
MA	0.61	1.02	0.61
PhD	1.26	3.15	1.26
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.02	1.16	1.02
BA # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.98 [†]	0.86	0.98 [†]
MA # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	0.88	1.00
PhD # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.98	0.86	0.98
Age	1.00	1.02	1.00
married	0.61	0.40 [†]	0.61
with partner	1.24	1.34	1.24
divorced/separated/widowed	1.32	2.19	1.32
one child	1.12	1.18	1.12
2+ children	2.05	3.10	2.05
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00		
one child # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
2+ children # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.89 [†]	0.83 [†]	0.89 [†]
hours worked from home (weekly) # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child [# hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00	1.00	1.00
2+ children [# hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00*	1.00 [†]	1.00*
lives in Romania/Moldova	0.98	0.91	0.98
total worked hours (weekly)	0.97 [†]	0.96	0.97 [†]
number of people in the household	1.07	1.08	1.07
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (FROM HOME)	1.01	1.04	1.01
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (FROM HOME) # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (total)	1.03**	1.05**	1.03**
Observations	109	109	109
Adjusted R ²	0.077		0.077
Pseudo R ²		0.158	

Exponentiated coefficients (OR).

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table A- 9. Prediction of taking breaks depending on previous experience of work-from-home: only those that have previous work-from-home experience

	tobit	OLS	ologit
has experience of isolation	0.97	1.05	0.97
knows someone with Covid-19 disease	1.01	1.09	1.01
income	1.00	1.00	1.00
woman	0.67	0.52*	0.67
BA	1.13	2.06	1.13
MA	0.37 [†]	0.26	0.37 [†]
PhD	1.32	2.13	1.32
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	0.87	1.00
BA # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.99	0.90	0.99
MA # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.01	0.94	1.01
PhD # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.99	0.90	0.99
Age	0.99	0.99	0.99
married	0.40*	0.23**	0.40*
with partner	1.10	0.93	1.10
divorced/separated/widowed	1.31	105.20	1.31
one child	1.11	1.67	1.11
2+ children	2.07	3.12	2.07
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.99	0.92	0.99
2+ children # hours worked from home (weekly)	0.93	0.87	0.93
hours worked from home (weekly) # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00	1.00
one child [# hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00	1.00 [†]	1.00
2+ children [# hours worked from home (weekly)] ²	1.00	1.00	1.00
lives in Romania/Moldova	1.45	1.57	1.45
total worked hours (weekly)	0.98	1.21	0.98
number of people in the household	1.15 [†]	1.37 [†]	1.15 [†]
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (FROM HOME)	1.03	1.19**	1.03
hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00		
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (FROM HOME) # hours worked from home (weekly)	1.00	1.00*	1.00
BEFORE pandemics: worked hours (total)	1.04**	1.07***	1.04**
Observations	77	77	77
Adjusted R ²	0.204		0.204
Pseudo R ²		0.310	

Exponentiated coefficients

[†] $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figures of marginal effects, including with confidence intervals

Up to this point, all figures were displayed without confidence intervals, in order to allow an easier reading of the direction of effects. In this section, all figures are re-drawn adding the 95% confidence intervals.

Figure A- 8. Marginal effects on taking breaks (Figure A- 5)

Upper-left pane (worked hours) based on model (1). Upper-right pane (age) is based on model (2). Bottom-left pane (children) is based on model (3). Bottom-right pane (education) is based on model (4). For all panes, the Y-axes have the same categories, illustrated on the right.

Figure A- 9. Marginal effects on taking breaks – only those that did not report too long hours (Figure A- 10)

Upper-left pane (worked hours) based on model (1). Upper-right pane (age) is based on model (2). Bottom-left pane (children) is based on model (3). Bottom-right pane (education) is based on model (4). For all panes, the Y-axes have the same categories, illustrated on the right.

Figure A- 11. Type of breaks & children: marginal effects based on logit models (Figure 2 – main text)

Figure A- 12. Joint marginal effects of having children and number of hours worked from home on the likelihood to take various types of breaks (logit models)

* In each pane, the probability to take at least a break varies from 0 to 100%.
When the number of cases is lower, the 95% CI were not estimated.